

1 **Thermal, food and vegetation effects on winter bird species richness of**
2 **Mediterranean oakwoods**

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12

13 **Abstract**

14 A better understanding of the species-energy relationship needs to be developed using
15 fine-grained approaches that involve the use of small geographical scales of known
16 characteristics, such as habitat heterogeneity, food availability, direct measures of
17 temperature, and functional groups of species. We carried out a two-year study to analyze
18 the effects of the thermal environment and food availability, while controlling for the
19 influence of habitat structure, on winter species richness of birds living in oakwoods of a
20 mountainous region of Central Spain of Mediterranean continental climate. The guild of
21 ground-foraging birds was selected as model organisms considering its susceptibility to
22 winter conditions associated to unpredictable snowfalls. The spatial variation in species
23 richness of this guild was determined by food availability, but only for those stable and
24 predictable resources not affected by frequent snowfalls (shrubs producing fruits; a
25 complete lack of association was found with arthropod abundance on ground). Thermal
26 effects directly associated with air temperature, and indirectly mediated by vegetation
27 structure providing a mosaic of sun-shade patches, were also very influential. These
28 patterns were highly repeatable across years. Daytime temperature had no influence
29 determining spatial variation in species richness, but night (minimum) temperature was a
30 very important predictor (explained considering the lower temperatures at night, the
31 longer duration of night, and the inability of diurnal birds to develop active behavioural
32 thermoregulation during nighttime). This result highlights the need to consider
33 physiological processes mediating the species-environment relationships when analyzing
34 the relationships between climatic variables and biodiversity phenomena.

35 **Keywords:** *ground-foraging birds; habitat structure; mountain forests; resource*
36 *availability; temperature.*

37

38 **Introduction**

39 Global biodiversity gradients are constrained by climate throughout the influence of
40 solar energy and water availability on trophic cascades, and the metabolic requirements
41 of organisms (Hawkins et al. 2003; Brown et al. 2004; Qian 2010 and references therein).
42 Nevertheless, the relationship between richness and temperature is dependent on
43 taxonomic groups and geographic areas, is a poor predictor of observed diversity
44 gradients in most terrestrial systems, and there is no evidence for a universal response of
45 diversity to temperature on a broad-scale basis (Hawkins et al. 2007; Whittaker et al.
46 2007). A good understanding of species-energy relationships needs to be developed,
47 mechanistically, on small geographical scales, as opposed to exploring relationships
48 between diversity and environment with grid data cells of hundreds or thousands of
49 square kilometers. For example, species-energy relationships may arise because high-
50 energy areas support more individuals, and these larger populations may buffer species
51 from extinction, although abundant species contribute more to species-energy
52 relationships than rare ones (Evans et al. 2005). This fine-grained approach involves
53 using spatial units of known characteristics, such as habitat heterogeneity, food
54 availability or direct measures of temperature, as well as differentiating among functional
55 groups of species (i.e., guilds; see for example, Evans et al. 2006; Carnicer and Díaz-
56 Delgado 2008; Honkanen et al. 2010).

57 Winter bird ranges and abundance are strongly associated with temperature (Root
58 1988a, 1988b; Canterbury 2002; La Sorte et al. 2009). The bases for these relationships
59 are founded on physiological limits and on the influence of temperature on food
60 availability. Physiological temperature limits are strongly correlated with the minimum
61 temperature during winter at the coldest limit of the boundary range, and thus species that
62 can tolerate cold temperatures with small relative increases in resting metabolic rate tend

63 to be found in cold environments (Canterbury 2002). On the other hand, food availability
64 is critical for winter survival of birds (Fretwell 1972; Newton 1980), throughout its
65 influence on the satisfaction of energy demands, on building up body reserves to
66 overcome fasting periods (e.g., the long winter night or during cold spells; Blem 1990;
67 Biebach 1996), and on breeding performance the following spring (Robb et al. 2008). For
68 example, Meehan et al. (2004) found that total abundance of wintering birds increased
69 with environmental productivity and decreases with environmental temperature when
70 individuals are below their thermoneutral zone (usually between 20 and 35 °C; Calder
71 and King 1974; Kendeigh et al. 1977). Cresswell et al. (2009) have shown that the
72 increase of 6.5 °C from 1995 to 2005 in mean daily winter temperature decreased the
73 starvation risk of great tits in England (birds responded to this scenario decreasing their
74 body mass), while Rogers and Reed (2003) showed how the ground-feeding finch *Junco*
75 *hyemalis* maximize winter survival probability by integrating multiple environmental
76 factors affecting starvation risk including temperature (but also snowfall frequency and
77 food availability).

78 Ground-foraging birds are a guild susceptible to winter conditions, especially in
79 mountain areas. Unpredictable snowfalls make food on forest floor –such as arthropods,
80 seeds or fruits on bushes– temporally unavailable, and snow cover lasts longer at higher
81 altitudes. On the other hand, fruit productivity and arthropod activity are lower with
82 decreasing temperatures and solar radiation (Honek 1997; Breckle 2002). Under these
83 circumstances, the selection of the optimal thermal environment is a basic mean of
84 obtaining an energy balance that results from the interaction between food intake and
85 energy expenditure (including basal, activity, digestive and thermoregulation costs). The
86 thermal environment is determined by the interaction of numerous factors, among which
87 temperature, wind and incidence of solar radiation stand out. Altitude is inversely related
88 to temperature and positively with snowfall probability and persistence, although terrain

89 effects can modify the adiabatic lapse rate (e.g., thermal inversion, exposure to sun
90 radiation according to cardinal orientation). Solar radiation modifies the thermal
91 environment patchily as a consequence of its incidence through vegetation screen,
92 offering a fine-grained mosaic of shade and lit areas.

93 This paper analyzes the effect of the thermal environment and food availability,
94 while controlling for the influence of habitat structure, on species richness of ground-
95 foraging birds living in oakwoods of a mountainous region of Central Spain, using a
96 landscape-scale approach (e.g., Turcotte and Desrochers 2005; Robb et al. 2008). The
97 winter bird community of these forests has been previously studied (Carrascal and Díaz
98 2006), but food availability was not measured and the thermal environment was inferred,
99 instead of measured, considering altitude and solar radiation according to cardinal
100 orientation of oakwood plots. We make two important, general, predictions explaining
101 the spatial variation of species richness of this foraging guild. First, air temperature will
102 be positively related to species richness, although minimum nighttime temperature will
103 be more important than maximum daytime temperature. This contrasting pattern
104 regarding ambient temperature may be understood considering the longer duration of
105 night, the lower values of nighttime temperature, and the limited ability of diurnal birds
106 to cope with thermoregulatory costs during nighttime by means of thermogenesis derived
107 from foraging activity (i.e., heat produced during exercise, Webster and Weathers 1990;
108 Cooper and Sonsthagen 2007). And second, spatial variation in species richness will track
109 food availability; especially for resources whose accessibility is less prone to be
110 constrained by unpredictable snowfalls (fruit availability in the understory should be
111 more important than arthropods on ground).

112

113 **Material and methods**

114 **Study area and period**

115 The study area was situated in the Sierra de Guadarrama (central Spain, 40°44'N,
116 03°58'W), covering ca. 500 km². The climate of this region is continental cold
117 Mediterranean climate, with abundant snowfalls and a large proportion of days with
118 minimum temperatures below 0 °C (respectively 25% and 52% of the days in December
119 and January of the study period 2008-2010; data from 6 meteorological stations located in
120 the study region; Spanish Agencia Estatal de Meteorología. Ministerio de Medio
121 Ambiente, y Medio Rural y Marino). We focused on 20 oakwood plots of 75 m in
122 diameter, located in four sectors of dense oakwoods (each sector larger than 3 km²: La
123 Herrería, La Golondrina, La Fuente del Cura and south slope of Morcuera Pass and north
124 slope of Morcuera Pass), with altitudes ranging from 1000 to 1600 m asl. Though all
125 consisting of monospecific forests of *Quercus pyrenaica* (a marcescent species typical of
126 southwestern Mediterranean mountains), oakwood plots were selected to cover a wide
127 range of variation in forest maturity, steepness and cardinal orientations of slopes and,
128 therefore, in the amount of received solar radiation on ground. Thermal inversion is a
129 common phenomenon in the study region (deviation from the normal negative decrease
130 of temperature with altitude).

131 The study was conducted during two consecutive winters, from 01-Dec-2008 to
132 31-Jan-2009 and from 01-Dec-2009 to 31-Jan-2010.

133 **Bird censuses and habitat structure**

134 We assessed bird species richness in 20 oakwood plots using point-count stations
135 (Bibby et al. 2000) lasting 10-min (i.e., the number of different species detected). The
136 settlement period prior to the point count starting was 5 min. All auditory and visual

137 contacts were recorded, but only those within a 75 m (1.77 ha) radius were used in
138 subsequent analyses, because a large proportion (76%) of the contacts were detected
139 within this census belt. Censuses were conducted by the same persons (LMC and JS) on
140 nearly windless (wind speed $< 3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and rainless days. We made an effort to improve
141 accuracy in distance estimates, and to reduce inter-observer variability, by training
142 continuously with a laser rangefinder to the cut-off point of 75 m. Plots were separated by
143 at least 300 m to minimize the probability of sampling the same birds more than once,
144 being the nearest oakwood plots separated by steep ridges. Average distance between
145 oakwood plots within the four forest sectors was 1206 m (range: 300 – 3693 m), while
146 average distance among the four forest sectors was 26.5 km (range: 8.2 – 41.3 km). Each
147 year, the censuses were repeated in three different days during December and January
148 (wintering season for all species), within the first 3 h of the morning and in the afternoon
149 beginning 2 h before sunset. Thus, each oakwood plot had an accumulated census time of
150 30 min, which is adequate for bird surveys of woodland birds during the non-breeding
151 season (Shiu and Lee 2003). Species richness was measured as the average number of
152 ground-foraging birds species per 10 min census, and bird abundance was estimated as
153 the average of bird counts across the three censuses (expressed in $\text{birds} \cdot 10 \text{ min}^{-1} \cdot 1.77 \text{ ha}^{-1}$
154 ¹).

155 Two adjacent 25-m-radius plots were placed within each oakwood plot to sample
156 vegetation structure, representing the total environmental heterogeneity within the census
157 plot. Measurements defining vegetation structure were covers of the tree and shrub layers
158 (distinguishing four bush types: oak regrowth $< 2 \text{ m}$ in height; thorny, fruit producing,
159 shrubs of genus *Crataegus*, *Rubus*, *Prunus* and *Rosa*; *Cistus* spp macchie shrubs; and
160 *Cytisus* and *Genista* brooms), average height of the shrub and tree layers, mean and
161 number of trunks within two diameter classes: 10-30 cm and more than 30 cm at the
162 breast level (see the Appendix for more details on habitat structure in the 20 study

163 oakwood plots). We assumed that cover of fruiting shrubs (*Crataegus*, *Rubus*, *Prunus* and
164 *Rosa*) was a surrogate of fruit availability (Shochat et al. 2002; Tellería et al. 2008). All
165 vegetation structure variables were visually estimated, after previous training, by LMC
166 and JS. See the Appendix for more details on ranges and mean values of habitat structure
167 variables in the 20 study oakwood plots.

168 **Focal species**

169 The study species belong to a ground-foraging guild whose species spend more than 80%
170 of feeding time on the ground (LM Carrascal, unpublished data; Cramp 1998 for general
171 details; Carrascal et al. 1987 for this group of species in forests of Central Spain). The
172 species included are (in decreasing order of abundance): blackbird, *Turdus merula*
173 (average of 0.25 birds per oakwood plot in the two study winters); mistle thrush, *Turdus*
174 *viscivorus* (0.24); redwing, *Turdus iliacus* (0.22); european robin, *Erithacus rubecula*
175 (0.16); chaffinch, *Fringilla coelebs* (0.14); eurasian wren, *Troglodytes troglodytes* (0.13);
176 song thrush, *Turdus philomelos* (0.09); citril bunting, *Emberiza cirlus* (0.05); rock
177 bunting, *Emberiza cia* (0.04); dunnock, *Prunella modularis* (0.03); black redstart,
178 *Phoenicurus ochruros* (0.02). The majority of these birds are facultative frugivores that
179 also include a large proportion of invertebrates in their diets (*Turdus merula*, *Turdus*
180 *viscivorus*, *Turdus iliacus*, *Erithacus rubecula* and *Turdus philomelos*; Guitián 1985;
181 Cramp 1998; these five species account for 70% of all detected individual birds in the
182 censuses carried out in the 20 woodland plots). A considerably smaller proportion of
183 birds wintering in these oakwoods rely mainly or exclusively on seeds or vegetal matter
184 (*Fringilla coelebs*, *Emberiza cirlus*, *Emberiza cia* and *Prunella modularis*; 19% of all
185 detected individual birds in the censuses). Finally, only *Troglodytes troglodytes* and
186 *Phoenicurus ochruros* were mainly insectivorous species (11% of all birds counted).

187 **Air temperatures**

188 To describe winter air temperature we set one temperature logger (Onset HOBO
189 Pendant) in each oakwood plot, placed on thick trunks, oriented to the north and at
190 approximately 1.5 m above ground. Data loggers recorded air temperature every ten
191 minutes from 01-Dec-2008 to 31-Jan-2009 and from 01-Dec-2009 to 31-Jan-2009. For
192 each recording day (144 measurements) we obtained average temperature, average
193 daytime temperature, average night temperature, maximum daytime temperature and
194 minimum night temperature. Temperatures for the 62 days of the study period were
195 averaged for each oakwood plot. All these five temperature measurements were highly
196 correlated across days and oakwood plots. Thus, and in order to avoid multicollinearity in
197 data analyses, we selected the two least correlated measurements: minimum night and
198 maximum daytime temperature. Moreover, these two temperatures have a clear
199 functional meaning related, respectively, to maximum thermoregulatory costs at night
200 and minimum thermoregulatory costs at daytime.

201 **Operative temperature and radiation on the ground**

202 As an approximation to the operative temperature experienced by foraging birds
203 on the ground, we used hollow copper cylinders (length 5 cm, diameter 1 cm) closed at
204 both ends except for a small fissure that allowed us to insert the sensing tip of an
205 electronic digital thermometer (digi-thermo; ± 0.1 °C precision). On calm days, this
206 environmental temperature integrates all the exogenous heat sources influencing a
207 foraging bird: radiation from the sun, conduction from the substrate and the effect of
208 wind on thermal conductance. We assume that these devices indicate the temperature a
209 bird would eventually reach if it did not have metabolic heat production. Previous
210 measurements showed that copper cylinders and taxidermic mounts (copper models
211 covered by passerine skins) eventually reached the same equilibrium temperatures (see

212 Carrascal et al. 2001 and references therein for more details on the application of this
213 technique to small forest bird species).

214 We selected 30 sampling points centered in the study area (Biological Station of
215 El Ventorrillo) that were sampled within seven hours around the zenith of cloudless and
216 windless days. In each sampling point we set two electronic digital thermometer-hollow
217 copper cylinders five cm above the forest floor separated 25-50 cm, one exposed to direct
218 sun radiation and another in deep shade (e.g. on a trunk shade). We distributed the two
219 thermometer-hollow copper cylinders so that they sampled the whole variability in
220 radiation intensity in the study forest on six different days (14th January to 10th February).
221 We also sampled air temperature at the same place using another thermometer-hollow
222 copper cylinder (located 1.5 m above ground, in the shade). Environmental temperatures
223 were registered three minutes after hollow copper cylinders were settled five cm above
224 the ground, to assure temperature measures were stabilized, and checking for its stability
225 during the next minute. Radiation intensity was also measured at each sampling point
226 with a PAR light sensor (Quantum QSO, measuring radiation from 400 to 700 nm). At
227 the end of the 3-min periods, we took 12 radiation measurements at 5-s intervals in the
228 same position where the thermometer-hollow copper cylinders were placed (incident
229 radiation was estimated as the average of these 12 measurements). Variation in operative
230 temperature was analyzed with a GLM regression model using air temperature and
231 radiation as predictor variables.

232 **Arthropod availability on ground**

233 Prey availability for ground-foraging species was estimated by counting all arthropods
234 longer than 1 mm found during visual searches of 2 min on patches of 50x50 cm² (see
235 Cooper and Whitmore 1990 and references therein). Counts were made in winter 2009-
236 2010 from 10 a.m. to 5 p.m., when temperatures reached higher values for arthropods to

237 be active. Ground patches were mainly composed of oak litter and were dry and clean of
238 snow during sampling. Arthropods were searched on the surface of the ground because
239 the study species are ground gleaners that do not dig or remove oak litter while foraging
240 for arthropods. Twenty patches were sampled in each oakwood plot within 50 m from
241 their centers. All prey items were identified to order and estimated to the nearest
242 millimeter *in situ* without collecting them. Dry body masses were estimated using the
243 allometric equations available in Díaz and Díaz (1991). No arthropods were found in
244 40.2% of the patches. Average encounter rate with arthropods was 1.29 arthropods / 2
245 min (n=400 2-min samples). The average length of the encountered arthropods was 3.78
246 mm (n=515 individuals), with an average dry mass of 2.02 mg. The main arthropod
247 groups were Hemiptera, which accounted for 47.6% of total individuals, Arachnids
248 20.6%, Orthoptera 8.7%, Diptera 6.2%, Coleoptera 5.0%, and Hymenoptera 4.9%.

249 **Data analyses**

250 The relationships between the response variable (species richness, i.e., average
251 number of ground-foraging birds species per 10 min census in winter 2009-2010) and
252 habitat structure variables, temperatures and arthropod availability (predictors) were
253 analysed by means of Partial Least Squares Regressions (hereafter PLSR; Abdi 2007),
254 using oakwood plots as sample units. Results obtained with PLSR are similar to those
255 from conventional multiple regression techniques; however, it is extremely robust to the
256 effects of sample size and degree of correlation between predictor variables, which makes
257 PLSR especially useful in cases of low sample size and severe multicollinearity
258 (Carrascal et al. 2009). Associations with the response variable are established with
259 factors extracted from predictor variables that maximize the explained variance in the
260 dependent variable. These factors are defined as linear combinations of independent
261 variables, so the original multidimensionality is reduced to a lower number of orthogonal

262 factors to detect structure in the relationships between predictor variables and between
263 these factors and the response variable. The extracted factors account for successively
264 lower proportions of original variance. The relative contribution of each variable to the
265 derived factors was calculated by means of the square of predictor weights. Only those
266 components significant after a five-fold validation procedure were retained.

267 Although only the results for average species richness of the study species are
268 presented, very similar results are obtained when analyzing data for the cumulative
269 number of species in the three censuses per oakwood plot, and the three most abundant
270 species. Therefore, and for the sake of brevity, we avoid the presentation of these results.

271 Variation in operative temperature 5 cm above ground was analyzed by means of
272 a [multiple regression](#), using solar radiation and air temperature (in the shade) as predictor
273 variables. Other statistical procedures used were paired t-tests, Pearson correlations, and
274 parallelism test (applying one-way ANCOVA with the two study winters as factor). All
275 the statistical analyses were carried out using Statistica 9.0 (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa,
276 Oklahoma).

277

278 **Results**

279 **Air temperatures**

280 The lowest minimum night temperatures in the 20 oakwood plots ranged between
281 -16.7 and -7.5 °C, while the maximum daytime temperatures ranged between 12.8 and
282 19.4 °C (see the Appendix for more details on ranges and mean air temperatures in the 20
283 oakwood plots). Thus, temperature throughout the study period was constantly below the
284 lower critical temperature, outside the thermoneutral range for a small passerine (usually
285 below 18 to 22 °C for many winter acclimated species in temperate areas; Calder & King

286 1974; Kendeigh et al. 1977). That is, the studied birds faced an environment that probably
287 required regulatory thermogenesis much of the time.

288 **Variation in operative temperature on the ground**

289 Average operative temperature 5 cm above ground under direct solar radiation
290 was 23.1 °C (sd = 6.06, n=30) in cloudless days from 10 h a.m to 5 h p.m., while it
291 decreased to 12.7 °C in the shade (sd = 2.16, n=30). These temperatures were recorded
292 under a broad variability in air temperature (-0.5 to 16 °C). The highest recorded
293 operative temperature exposed to full sun at midday was 34.3 °C in a warm winter day
294 when air temperature was 13.9 °C. The average difference in operative temperatures 5 cm
295 above ground between full sun – shade exposition was 10.4 °C, with a relatively low
296 coefficient of variation (43.7 %). Therefore, birds foraging on the ground exposed to
297 direct sun radiation, instead of on the ground in deep shade, obtained a considerable
298 thermal benefit during winter in the study oakwoods.

299 Operative temperature 5 cm above ground was a very deterministic phenomenon
300 ($R^2 = 89.2\%$; $F = 235.2$, $df = 2, 57$, $P \ll 0.001$). Solar radiation was the most important
301 factor explaining variation in operative temperature (standardized regression coefficient,
302 $\beta = 0.86$, $P \ll 0.001$; partial effect: 70.4% of variance). Air temperature (in the shade)
303 was also significantly and positively associated with operative temperature ($\beta = 0.23$,
304 $P \ll 0.001$; partial effect: 4.8% of variance).

305 **Variation in species richness and microclimate across woodlands and years**

306 Average air temperature was highly correlated with minimum night temperature
307 across oakwood plots in the two study winters 2008-2009 and 2009-2010 (Pearson
308 correlation coefficients are, respectively, 0.975 and 0.972, n=20 and $P \ll 0.001$). Average
309 temperature reached significantly lower figures in winter 2009-2010 than in 2008-2009;

310 0.68 °C lower in 2009-2010; 95% confidence interval: 0.54 – 0.81 °C (paired t-test:
311 $P < < 0.001$; Figure 1A).

312 Average number of ground-foraging species per oakwood plot was highly and
313 significantly correlated in the two study winters ($r=0.873$, $n=20$, $P < 0.001$). The same
314 result was obtained for the accumulated number of species detected in the three censuses
315 ($r=0.793$, $P < 0.001$). Species richness was significantly lower in winter 2009-2010 than in
316 2008-2009 for both average number of species per census (Figure 1B) and the
317 accumulated number of ground-foraging species ($P < 0.005$ in the two paired t-tests).

318 In summary, differences in microclimatic conditions and bird species richness
319 among oakwood plots were repeatable across years. Number of ground-foraging species
320 per plot was lower in the colder and cloudier winter (2009-2010) than in the warmer and
321 sunnier one (2008-2009).

322 **Spatial variation in species richness of ground-foraging birds**

323 Species richness and abundance of ground-foraging birds were highly correlated
324 in both study winters: $r=0.942$ for winter 2008-2009 and $r=0.974$ for winter 2009-2010
325 ($n=20$ woodland plots and $P < 0.001$ for both correlations; Figure 2). The regression slopes
326 did not significantly differ between winters 2008-2009 and 2009-2010 (parallelism test:
327 $F_{1,36}=3.14$, $P=0.09$). Therefore, species richness increases just because there are more
328 individuals, and this pattern did not change between consecutive winters.

329 Two significant components, accounting for 87.5% of total variance in species
330 richness, were obtained in the PLSR analysis with the 20 oakwood plots in winter 2009-
331 2010, when arthropod availability was sampled (Table 1). Residuals of this PLSR model
332 did not differ among the four forest sectors ($F_{3,16}=2.47$, $P=0.1$). The most influential
333 variables in this PLSR model were cover of thorny, fruit producing, shrubs, average night
334 minimum temperature, altitude, density of large and medium sized oaks (trunk diameter

335 at breast height >30 cm and 10-30 cm, respectively), and oak average height (i.e., they
336 summarized 90.6% of the information content of predictor variables explaining ground-
337 foraging species richness; percentage obtained adding the squares of variable importances
338 in Table 1). Conversely, diurnal maximum temperature and arthropod availability on
339 ground had no influence explaining inter-plot differences in species richness (see variable
340 importances in Table 1).

341 The first PLSR component (79.1% of variance, $P < 0.001$) was positively
342 associated with cover of thorny shrubs producing fruits and minimum night temperature,
343 while it was negatively related to altitude (these three variables were responsible of
344 75.2% of the information content of this component). Thus, oakwood plots located at
345 lower altitudes, with a dense cover of thorny shrubs producing fruits, and with higher
346 minimum night temperatures had higher number of species foraging on the ground
347 (Figure 3). The second PLSR component, although quantitatively of lower importance
348 (8.5% of variance, $P = 0.003$), was mainly related (negatively) to oak cover (both tree and
349 regrowth layers), average tree height, and density of medium sized oaks. Thus, species
350 richness of ground-foraging birds decreased with maturity and development of the tree
351 layer and cover of oak regrowth: mature and dense oakwoods plots maintained a lower
352 number of species of this foraging guild.

353

354 **Discussion**

355 **Abiotic effects of temperature and altitude**

356 Our results show that temperature plays an important role in determining the
357 spatial variation in species richness of this guild of ground-foragers during winter.
358 Moreover, this within-year pattern is also observed in the between-year analysis: the
359 number of ground-foraging species per oakwood plot is lower in the colder winter despite

360 between-years difference in average air temperature is as low as 0.68 °C. The mechanistic
361 link between species richness and temperature can be understood as a deterministic
362 outcome of physiological processes, because temperature affects the metabolism of
363 individuals, and species richness increases just because there are more individuals per
364 woodland plot (see Figure 2). Low temperatures and long nights of winter are associated
365 with an increased risk of starvation through body reserves regulation (e.g., Cresswell
366 1998; Gosler 2002; Macleod et al. 2005; Krams et al. 2010). Temperature determines
367 metabolic expenditure of birds below the thermoneutral zone, the lower limit being
368 around 20 °C for many winter acclimated species in temperate areas (Calder and King
369 1974; Kendeigh et al. 1977). Temperature in our study area is considerably lower than the
370 lower critical temperature, ranging from 4.5 to 8.9 °C for average maximum diurnal
371 temperature, and -3.2 to 1.2 °C for average minimum nocturnal temperature. Thus,
372 overwintering in these continental Mediterranean oakwoods is energetically demanding
373 in terms of thermoregulatory metabolic costs.

374 Nevertheless, winter temperature has a different meaning for this group of birds
375 depending upon what temperature is considered. Daytime (maximum) temperature has no
376 influence explaining spatial variation in species richness, but night (minimum)
377 temperature is a very important predictor according to its variable importance in the
378 PLSR analysis. This contrasting pattern of covariation with species richness may be
379 easily explained considering the low temperatures attained during night and the
380 considerably longer duration of night (average duration of night: day during the study
381 period = 14.4 h : 9.6 h). Whenever not sleeping, heat production resulting from locomotor
382 muscles during foraging activity and from food assimilation, can account for part of
383 thermoregulatory requirements in the cold for diving, glean-and-hang foraging species, as
384 well as in ground-foraging birds (Webster and Weathers 1990; Dawson and O'Connor
385 1996; Kaseloo and Lovvorn 2006; Cooper and Sonsthagen 2007). On the other hand,

386 small passerines are able to compensate for low air temperatures behaviourally, by
387 spending more time in sunlit patches while foraging (Carrascal et al. 2001). The
388 contrasting effects of temperature on bird species richness suggest the need to consider
389 with caution any attempt to relate climatic variables to biological phenomena
390 simplistically, with disregard to the autoecological and physiological processes mediating
391 the species-environment relationships.

392 Finally, the great negative influence of altitude determining the observed pattern
393 of species richness is probably a combination of temperature (discussed above) and
394 snow-mediated effects. Snow cover forces birds to shift their foraging behaviour or
395 migrate (Brotons 1997; Nakamura and Shindo 2001); thus, snowfall frequency and
396 persistence may be considered as a surrogate measure of resource deterioration. At higher
397 altitudes, snowfall probability increases while snow cover lasts longer, constraining food
398 searching on the ground, and thus determining the observed reduction in species richness
399 with altitude.

400 **Biotic effects of vegetation structure and food resources**

401 Food availability has been proposed to drive winter distribution in small birds (see
402 review in Newton 1980; Wiens 1989), although its effect depends on the ability of birds
403 to efficiently track its spatio-temporal distribution (Shochat et al. 2002). A greater
404 abundance of food resources would reduce the amount of time required for searching
405 during the few light hours of winter days, and increase the rate of food intake in order not
406 to starve. Therefore, food abundance should be an important factor determining
407 population density and habitat selection through foraging efficiency. Nevertheless,
408 previous research with both frugivorous and insectivorous birds have reported a mixed
409 bag of results, as in some studies food abundance has been found to be important whereas
410 in other studies its effect was negligible (see examples for the Iberian Peninsula in

411 Herrera 1998; Carrascal et al. 2001; García and Ortiz-Pulido 2004; Tellería and Pérez-
412 Tris 2003, 2007; Tellería et al. 2008).

413 Resources like arthropods or seeds on the forest floor of Pyrenean oakwoods are
414 scarce and highly unpredictable for ground-foraging birds living in mountainous areas,
415 where snowfalls severely constrain its accessibility. In winter, the grass layer is nearly
416 absent in these forests, and the seed bank produced during summer is completely covered
417 by a dense layer of leaves fallen during autumn. This is the reason why granivorous birds
418 are so scarce in dense deciduous forests during winter in the Mediterranean region
419 (Tellería et al. 1988). On the other hand, arthropods are very scarce according to a very
420 low encountering rate with them (1.29 arthropods / 2 min) and their average low body
421 masses (dry mass of 2.02 mg). These facts, together with the impossibility of having a
422 sure access to this resource throughout the winter due to snowfall unpredictability, could
423 explain the almost null effect of arthropod biomass on species richness found in this
424 study.

425 Conversely, cover of fruit producing shrubs (as a surrogate of fruit availability) is
426 the best predictor of species richness of ground-foraging bird in the Pyrenean oakwoods,
427 indicating that this group of species (mainly dominated by facultative frugivorous
428 species) is food limited during winter time and that they track the spatial patterning of
429 fruit producing shrubs (see also Guitián and Munilla 2008 and Tellería et al. 2008 for bird
430 and fruit abundance in scrublands and woodlands of northern and southern Spain). The
431 cover of other shrubs does not exert any influence on species richness of ground-
432 foraging birds. Snow cover scarcely affects availability of fruits in shrubs, which could in
433 turn be a highly predictable food resource. On the other hand, as these fruit producing
434 shrubs (*Rosa*, *Prunus*, *Crataegus*, *Rubus* species) are thorny and grow in dense patches,
435 they may play an additional role providing protection against predators while foraging on
436 the ground.

437 Other habitat structure variable related to bird species richness is tree maturity
438 (tree thickness, cover and height), explaining a considerably lower amount of variance.
439 Nevertheless, and in contrast with other bird guilds for which positive relationships have
440 been found (e.g., Turcotte and Desrochers 2005; Carrascal and Díaz 2006; Godinho et al.
441 2010; Honkanen et al. 2010), species richness of ground-foraging birds decreases with
442 maturity and development of the tree layer. The unexpected negative influence of forest
443 maturity on bird species richness of this foraging guild may be explained by considering
444 the detrimental effect of shadow projection on thermoregulation during normal foraging
445 activities on forest floor: mature forests have a well developed tree crown projecting
446 more shadows where operative temperatures are considerably lower than in patches with
447 incident sun radiation (see Carrascal et al. 2001 for empirical evidence on behavioural
448 patch selection with *Certhia brachydactyla*). Operative temperature on ground is very
449 predictable, and the received sun radiation explains 70% of its variation. Thus, the
450 thermal benefit obtained by a bird staying on ground exposed to sun instead of in the
451 shade is, on average, 10.4 °C. Complementarily, this increased temperature could have a
452 positive, indirect, effect on foraging efficiency through the activation of arthropods at
453 higher temperatures (Avery and Krebs 1984; Carrascal et al. 2001), which would lead
454 birds in sunlit patches to achieve higher foraging success. Therefore, small-scale effects
455 mediated by the interaction sun radiation - vegetation structure may enhance the role of
456 the thermal state of the environment on bird species richness.

457 In conclusion, regional variation of small scale (~1-2 ha) species richness of the
458 ground-foraging guild of birds wintering in oakwoods of mountainous areas in Central
459 Spain is mainly determined by cover of fruit producing shrubs followed by thermal
460 effects, directly associated with minimum temperature during the long winter nights.
461 Thus, food availability is very influential, but only for those stable and predictable
462 resources (shrubs producing fruits), not affected by frequent snowfalls (i.e., null influence

463 of arthropods on ground). These patterns are highly repeatable across years, and support
464 the species-energy relationship at small spatial scales, as high-energy areas with higher
465 temperatures and more resources (fruits) support larger bird abundances that buffer
466 species from local disappearance. The marked difference in the influence of diurnal (null)
467 and nocturnal (very positive) temperatures on the regional variation in species richness
468 highlights the need to consider physiological processes mediating the species-
469 environment relationships when analyzing the relationships between climatic variables
470 and biodiversity phenomena.

471

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476

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638

639 **Fig. 1** Relationship between a) average temperature and b) average number of species per
640 census in winters (December - January) 2008-2009 and 2009-2010 in Central Spain. The
641 study species are *Emberiza cirulus*, *E. cia*, *Erithacus rubecula*, *Fringilla coelebs*,
642 *Phoenicurus ochruros*, *Prunella modularis*, *Troglodytes troglodytes*, *Turdus iliacus*, *T.*
643 *merula*, *T. philomelos* and *T. viscivorus*. Sample size is 20 oakwood plots and p-values
644 are $P=0.0000$ in both cases. Dashed line denotes what would be the identity between
645 measures in both years; continuous line is the regression line between data in the two
646 study winters

647

648 **Fig. 2** Relationship between species richness and bird abundance of ground-foraging
649 birds per woodland plot of 1.77 ha in two consecutive winters in Central Spain. Dots and
650 continuous line: winter (December - January) 2008-2009. Box and dashed line: 2009-
651 2010. Data refers to the average of three censuses in 20 woodland plots. Several data
652 points are completely overlapped.

653

654 **Fig. 3** Relationship between ground-foraging species richness and the two first
655 components of a partial least squares regression analysis (PLSR; see Table 1). The b)
656 second PLSR component; analyzes the residuals of the relationship depicted by the a)
657 first PLSR component, according to the sequential variance extraction carried out by
658 PLSR models. Sample size is 20 oakwood plots located in Central Spain in winter 2009-
659 2010 and p-values are $P=0.0026$ and $P=0.0000$, respectively

660

661

662 Figure 1

663

664

665 Figure 2

666

667 Figure 3

668

669 **Table 1:** Results of the partial least squares regression (PLSR) model explaining species
670 richness of ground-foraging birds in 20 oakwood plots in Central Spain in winter 2009-
671 2010. VarImp: variable importance in the PLSR model with two components. Figures
672 under PLSR-1 and PLSR-2 are the predictor weights of each variable in each component;
673 only relationships between individual variables and PLSR components with $|\text{weights}| > 0.3$
674 are shown
675

	VarImp	PLSR-1	PLSR-2
Cover of thorny, fruit producing, shrubs	0.513	0.53	
Average minimum night temperature	0.465	0.48	
Altitude	0.463	-0.49	
Density of large sized oaks (trunks > 30 cm dbh)	0.312		-0.45
Density of medium sized oaks (trunks 10-30 cm dbh)	0.248		
Average oak height	0.231		-0.46
Tree layer cover	0.170		-0.34
Cover of Cytisus and Genista shrubs	0.169		
Average shrub layer height	0.116		
Cover of oak regrowth (< 2 m in height)	0.096		-0.30
Average maximum diurnal temperature	0.085		
Cover of Cistus spp shrubs	0.075		
Arthropod biomass on ground	0.028		
R^2 by PLSR components		0.791	0.085

676

677

678 *Appendix.*

679 Mean and range (min / max) of study variables in 20 oakwood plots in Central Spain
 680 during winters 2008-2009 and 2009-2010. Number of ground-foraging species refer to
 681 census plots 75 m in diameter.

	mean	range
Cumulative number of ground-foraging species (in 3 censuses)	1.85	0 / 7
Average number of ground-foraging species (in 3 censuses)	1.09	0 / 3
Altitude (m)	1282	976 / 1597
Light intensity at midday ($\text{lux} \cdot 10^{-3}$); two winters	12.8	4.1 / 21.9
Average air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); two winters	1.44	-0.1 / 3.7
Average maximum diurnal temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); two winters	7.05	4.5 / 8.9
Average minimum night temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); two winters	-0.75	-3.0 / 1.2
Arthropod biomass on ground (dry mass, mg, per 2 minutes)	26.6	4 / 108
Cover of thorny, fruit producing, shrubs (<i>Crataegus</i> , <i>Rubus</i> , <i>Rosa</i>) (%)	4.3	0 / 45
Cover of maquis (<i>Cistus</i>) shrubs (%)	2.3	0 / 36
Cover of brooms (<i>Cytisus</i> and <i>Genista</i> shrubs) (%)	9.4	0 / 37
Cover of oak regrowth (< 2 m in height) (%)	5.0	0 / 19
Average shrub layer height (m)	1.0	0.33 / 2.40
Tree layer cover (%)	62.6	24 / 90
Average oak height (m)	10.8	6 / 16
Density of medium sized oaks (trunks 10-30 cm dbh in 0.2 ha)	99	28 / 205
Density of large sized oaks (trunks > 30 cm dbh in 0.2 ha)	7	0 / 31

682